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Research

Article

**LEVEL OF MICRO NUTRIENTS AMONG HEPATITIS
PATIENTS IN PAKISTAN**Dr Fatima Suraj¹, Dr Adila Farrukh¹, Dr Amna Tariq²¹Lahore General Hospital, Lahore²House Officer at Allied Hospital, Faisalabad

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Abstract:

Objective of the study: The basic aim of the study is to find the level of micronutrients in hepatitis patients. **Methodology of the study:** This cross-sectional study was conducted at Lahore General Hospital, Lahore during March 2019 to December 2019. The study was conducted according to the rules and regulations of concerned committee. The data were collected from 100 patients of both genders. Detailed history was taken from all patients with special reference to duration of hepatitis, mode of infection, previous history of jaundice, HBV or HCV infection. A thorough clinical examination was carried out and stigmata of chronic liver disease, hepatosplenomegaly, ascites, etc. if present were noted. **Results:** The demographic values of patient group and control group shows a significant difference. The data suggest clearly that CD4 count decreases in abnormal liver function. The results shown the table 02 demonstrates the multiple comparison of micronutrients level among patients and normal group. There was non-significant relationship present in diseased group treated with different therapies like interferon and glutathione as as $p < 0.05$. The level of micronutrients become decreases in diseased group. **Conclusion:** It is concluded that hepatitis directly increases the liver enzymes even after receiving medication and other therapies.

Corresponding author:

Dr. Fatima Suraj,

Lahore General Hospital, Lahore

QR code

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INTRODUCTION:

Liver is a pivotal organ of the body and play very important role in the metabolism. If there is any problem in the liver then the herbs or different plants play an important role for the treatment of liver disorders¹. There are a number of plants which shows hepatoprotective property. Hepatitis B and C viruses can lead to hepatocellular carcinoma and cirrhosis-related end-stage liver disease, which are potentially life-threatening liver diseases. Hepatitis B and C need immediate worldwide attention as the infection rates are too high. More than 240 million people globally have chronic (long-term) liver infections. Every year, about 600,000 people die because of the acute or chronic consequences of hepatitis B, and more than 350,000 people die from hepatitis C-related liver diseases worldwide².

Hepatitis is a major public health problem and is endemic throughout the world especially in tropical and developing countries. Hepatitis means inflammation of the liver. The liver is indispensable to our survival³. It has synthetic, storage and detoxification functions. An abnormal LFT may signify a serious disease that can be identified only through further testing. These conditions include liver diseases, such as primary biliary cirrhosis (PBC), diseases of other organs such as Paget's disease of bone, and multi-organ diseases such as haemochromatosis. However, the majority of people with an abnormal LFT in primary care settings will not have any such previously undetected disease⁴. They will have either no disease at all, or will be manifesting the effects of alcohol abuse or obesity. The doctor is likely to be aware, or at least suspicious, of these behaviors when ordering LFTs, but this does not exclude the presence of other diseases that may aggravate liver damage. There is thus a real question about which specific further tests, if any, a GP should order when an abnormal

LFT result is obtained in a patient with non-specific symptoms, or as a result of routine testing⁵.

Objective of the study

The basic aim of the study is to find the level of micronutrients in hepatitis patients among local population of Pakistan.

METHODOLOGY OF THE STUDY:

This cross-sectional study was conducted at Lahore General Hospital, Lahore during March 2019 to December 2019. The data were collected from 100 patients of both genders. Detailed history was taken from all patients with special reference to duration of hepatitis, mode of infection, previous history of jaundice, HBV or HCV infection. A thorough clinical examination was carried out and stigmata of chronic liver disease, hepatosplenomegaly, ascites, etc. if present were noted.

Blood analysis includes Hemoglobin (Hb), total leucocytes count (TLC), differential leucocytes count (DLC), platelet count, level of micronutrients and LFT were done in all patients. The LFT included serum bilirubin, aspartate aminotransferase (AST), alanine aminotransferase (ALT), serum alkaline phosphatase (SAP) and serum albumin. Abnormal values were defined as serum Bilirubin ≥ 1.5 mg/dl, ALT/AST ≥ 50 IU/ml.

Statistical analysis

The data were sampled and entered into the SPSS worksheet for analysis. The alpha criterion was set at 0.05.

RESULTS:

The demographic values of patient group and control group shows a significant difference. The data suggest clearly that CD4 count decreases in abnormal liver function. The results shown the table 02 demonstrates the multiple comparison of micronutrients level among patients and normal group. There were non-significant relationship present in diseased group treated with different therapies like interferon and glutathione as $p < 0.05$. The level of micronutrients become decreases in diseased group.

Table 01: Associations of Clinical Parameters with Abnormal Liver Function Tests

Parameter	Normal LFTs	Abnormal LFTs	P value
Age (years)	35.3 + 6.7	36.5 + 10.1	0.54
Sex (M:F)	237:35 (87.1%:12.5%)	45:3 (93.8%:6.2%)	0.91
BMI (kg/m ²)	21.8 ± 1.8	21.7 ± 2.7	0.88
Duration of HIV infection (months)	36 ± 50.3	38 ± 43.8	0.95
CD4 count (/mm ³)	280 ± 182	234 ± 212	0.12
Significant alcohol consumption	106 (38.9%)	24 (50%)	0.15
HBV & HCV Co-infection	47 (17.2%)	19 (39.6%)	0.002
HBsAg positive	26 (9.6%)	11 (22.9%)	0.01
Anti HCV positive	21 (7.7%)	06 (12.5%)	0.27

Table 02: Analysis of micronutrients in control group and diseased group

	F	Sig.	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Std. Error Difference
Zinc	1.668	.208	3.798	25	.001	31.206435
			3.531	15.155	.003	33.564560
Iron	24.927	.000	4.189	25	.000	.321750
			3.336	10.037	.008	.404044
Silinium	1.592	.219	17.193	25	.000	.340691
			16.431	16.498	.000	.356485

DISCUSSION:

Damage to the structural integrity of liver is reflected by an increase in the level of serum transaminase because these are cytoplasmic in location and are released into circulation after cellular damage⁸. It is generally accepted that the toxicity of carbon tetrachloride depends on the cleavage of the carbon-chlorine bond to generate a trichloromethyl free radical, and this free radical reacts rapidly with oxygen to form a trichloro methyl peroxy radical, which may contribute to the hepatotoxicity and subsequent increase in hepatic enzymes⁹.

Essential micronutrients are involved in many metabolic pathways in the liver, such as enzymatic functions and protein synthesis, oxidative damage and anti-oxidant defense, immunological competence, interferon therapy response regulations, and alterations of the virus genomes. Reactive oxygen species (ROS) have also been implicated in a number of hepatic pathologies in exacerbating liver diseases¹⁰.

CONCLUSION:

It is concluded that hepatitis directly increases the liver enzymes even after receiving medication and other therapies. The distribution of micronutrients activities in blood may be an additional host-specific parameter with a predictive value for the responsiveness of patients to interferon therapy.

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